

A NEW METHOD TO DETERMINE THE FIBRE/MATRIX BOND STRENGTH

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ABSTRACT

In the present paper a new method to determine the fibre/matrix bond strength in carbon fibre reinforced plastics (CFRP) is described. This method is based on the phenomenon of multiple cracking, which generally occurs in the transverse ply of a cross-ply 0/90/0 laminate. It is possible to determine the bond strength with the aid of the crack data of only one specimen. This is done by dividing the specimen in a number of elements all of which can fail. Two-parameter Weibull distributions proved to describe the fracture data very well. The first crack occurs at the biggest defect and the following cracks occur at smaller and smaller defects. The strongest element can be considered practically defect-free and thus fracture of this element will be caused by fracture of the weakest of either the matrix or the interface. The fracture strain of this element is determined by extrapolation of the determined Weibull distribution.

INTRODUCTION

In the past decades, during the development of different fibres and composites, the fibre/matrix bond strength was always regarded as an important property. The determination of this bond strength is not an easy task. Several applied techniques based on specimens with an embedded single filament are:

1. pull-out test^{1,2}
2. single fibre fragmentation test^{3,4}
3. micro-debond test⁵
(pressing a micro-indenter on a fibre in fibre direction of a polished cross-section of a specimen)
4. trapezoidal specimen with a single fibre⁶ under compression

With the aid of these techniques a shear bond strength is determined. The last mentioned method can also supply a tensile bond strength by making use of a curved trapezoidal specimen⁶. The determination of a fibre/matrix bond strength on commercially available material systems, however, seems not yet to be possible. In many cases the short beam shear strength is used as an indication of the quality of the bond strength. In recent years the use of thermoplastics as matrix systems has shown the limitations of this test technique. For this reason it is worthwhile to develop another test technique to determine the fibre/matrix bond strength. Norita et al⁷ have shown that besides the short beam shear strength also the inplane shear strength (measured on $\pm 45^\circ$ laminates) and the transverse strength are sensitive to the bond strength. Numerous investigations on transverse cracking in different

fibre reinforced plastics⁸⁻¹³ have shown that transverse cracking is mainly influenced by:

- the properties of the fibre
- the properties of the matrix
- the fibre volume fraction and fibre distribution
- the quality of the interface
- the defect distribution
- the constraining influence of neighbouring layers

If we like to develop a technique to measure the bond strength based on transverse cracking, we have to exclude the influence of the other parameters. The influence of the fibre/matrix bond strength on transverse cracking in one particular type of fibre reinforced plastics (with a certain fibre volume) can only be studied in connection with the influence of the defects and of constraint. This, because it is practically impossible to change the fibre/matrix bond strength (for instance by a fibre surface treatment or by applying a sizing) without also changing the defect distribution (caused by different wetting characteristics). Constraint reduces the severity of defects and thus these parameter defects and constraint have to be studied in relation with each other.

A direct measurement of the fibre/matrix bond strength with the aid of transverse cracking is possible if we could produce defect-free material, so that we don't have to consider the influence of constraint and the defects. This, of course, is not possible.

Investigations on multiple transverse cracking in CFRP 0/90/0 laminates (with thermoset matrix systems) have, however, shown that this bond strength (in the absence of defects) can be found by extrapolation of the fracture strength data of only one specimen. The procedure followed is to divide the specimen in a number of elements all of which can fail. The first element that fails contains the biggest defect, the last element that fails the smallest. Generally, a number of elements remain unbroken before the specimen fails due to rupture of the load bearing 0° plies. The failure strain of these unbroken elements can be determined by the extrapolation of the failure distribution curve. It will be shown that for a macroscopical and microscopical defect-free material the failure strain of the strongest element can be accepted as the weakest of either the interface or the matrix.

ANALYSIS

The occurrence of multiple cracking in the transverse ply of cross-ply laminates makes it reasonable to determine the transverse fracture strain distribution with the fracture data of only one specimen⁹⁻¹³. For this method it is necessary to divide the specimen in a number of elements all of which can fail and to register the strain at failure of every element that fails. The element length is determined with the expression, derived with the aid of a shear lag analysis,

$$\sigma_{2,x} = \sigma_{2,\infty} [1 - \exp - (\gamma x)] \quad (1)$$

which describes the stress recovery as a function of x near an existing crack (at $x=0$)^{8,9}. The stress $\sigma_{2,\infty}$ is the undisturbed stress at infinity $x=\infty$ (thermal plus mechanical stress) and γ is given by

$$\gamma = \sqrt{G/b(1/(E_1 \cdot a_1) + 2/(E_2 \cdot a_2))} \quad (2)$$

in which b is the width of the shear transfer layer and a_1 and a_2 are the thickness of the surface and 90° plies, respectively. A piezoelectric transducer registers the load drop due to a sudden transverse crack formation^{9,10} and thus the fracture strain for every occurring element failure can be measured. The result of the experiment on one single specimen is a list of occurred cracks with the respective fracture strains. These fracture data can be described with the aid of a two-parameter Weibull distribution⁹⁻¹³. The probability of element failure F according to this statistical distribution is given by:

$$F = 1 - \exp - (\epsilon_{f,1}^* / \hat{\epsilon}_{f,1}^*)^a \quad (3)$$

where $\epsilon_{f,1}^*$ is the strain ($= \epsilon_{2,\infty}$, consisting of a thermal as well as a mechanical component) and with "a" and $\hat{\epsilon}_{f,1}^*$ being the two Weibull parameters (shape parameter and characteristic fracture strain, respectively). Figure 1, as an example, shows that the fracture data correspond very well with the presented two-parameter Weibull distribution; a best fit making use of least square analysis and linear regression. It is clear that the first occurring crack is caused by the biggest flaw, as schematically presented in Fig. 2. Moving on the element fracture strain distribution curve to its top, fracture of the respective elements is caused by smaller and smaller defects. If we assume that the last breaking element is free of defects (which can only be said of macroscopically and microscopically void free material), then this fracture strain can be accepted as an interface failure strain, or in case the interface is weaker than the matrix, as an ultimate matrix strain. The gage length of the specimen being $l = 100$ mm contains roughly 100 to 200 elements and thus the strain at interface failure can be calculated by substituting the corresponding value of $F = 0.99$ to 0.995 ($= j/N+1 = 100/101$ or $200/201$) in eq. 3.

This interface fracture strain can only be accepted as a material property, if e.g. it is independent of the transverse ply thickness. Figure 3 published before presents the Weibull distribution of transverse plies with a different thickness (90_{12} , 90_6 and 90_4 , respectively). They appear to intersect in the right hand upper corner. Making use of the definition given above that interface failure occurs at $0.99 < F < 0.995$, a transverse strain at interface failure is determined ranging from 1.75 to 1.92 %. This variation in interface strength of 10 % is acceptably small compared with the variation of thickness of the 90° ply (by a factor of 3).

Thus, this ultimate transverse fracture strain (defined as strain at interface failure) can be accepted as a material property.

THE STRENGTH OF THE INTERFACE AS A FUNCTION OF THE TEMPERATURE

Recently the influence of the test temperature on transverse cracking and the interface strength were investigated on specimens of the laminate 0/90/0 out of the system T800/Fibredux 6376¹³. Tests were performed at 100°C , -40°C , RT $+60^\circ\text{C}$ and 100°C , respectively. The material was in a dry condition. From the determined Weibull distributions at each test temperature the characteristic fracture strain for first ply failure (FPF) for 100 mm long specimens and the strain at interface failure according to the procedure mentioned above were calculated. The results in Fig. 4 show that in the range of RT to 60°C the strain at interface failure is reduced severely. The strain at first ply failure generally increases, except in the aforementioned range where the strain at interface failure drops considerably.

The increase of the strain at FPF at increasing temperature is caused by the improved ductility of the matrix. Thus the influence of improved ductility dominates the strain at FPF except in the range RT to 60 °C.

CONCLUSION

The transverse fracture strain in carbon fibre reinforced plastics with thermoset matrix can be described very well with the aid of two-parameter Weibull distributions. These distributions can be determined with the crack data of only one specimen by dividing the specimen in a number of elements all of which can fail. The procedure to determine the fibre/matrix bond strength with the aid of these Weibull distributions is based on the assumption that the strongest element practically does not contain any defects, so that its failure strain reflects the strength of either the matrix or the interface. As the failure strain of the strongest elements generally is not reached at specimen failure, the interface failure strain cannot be measured directly, but must be calculated by extrapolation of the Weibull fracture strain distribution.

Comparison of the interface failure strain for different transverse ply thickness (90₁₂, 90₆ and 90₄) show that this failure strain really is a material property.⁶ Further⁴ the phenomenon of transverse cracking in a laminate 0/90₄/0 in the temperature range of -100 °C to +100 °C could be explained⁴ very well with the dependency of the transverse interface strength on the temperature.

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Fig. 1 Example of a two-parameter Weibull distribution based on the fracture data of only one specimen⁷³.

Fig. 2 Schematical presentation of the Weibull distribution of transverse plies and the derived transverse strain at interface failure.

Fig. 3 Weibull fracture strain distributions of CFRP transverse plies with a different thickness⁹.

Fig. 4 The strain at first ply failure (FPF) and at interface failure as a function of the test temperature (CFRP, TS00/6376¹³).